

Supplemental File 1: Overview of Dose Adjustment for Normal Eating (DAFNE)

DAFNE is a 5-day (or week) training course for people with type 1 diabetes. Courses are designed for people on MDI (multiple daily injections) unless specified as pump courses.

Fully remote formats were launched in July 2020 in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Whereas with face-to-face formats all learning is delivered in person, with remote formats most learning is self-directed, with synchronous group sessions to provide peer support. Since COVID-19, more DAFNE Central administrators started offering the DAFNE 'buddy' system which involves a call twice a year to offer support, for example, with entering data, training etc. Any issues are fed back to either clinical educators / trainers or operational staff. DAFNE training and delivery has also moved online.

Face to face (F2F) courses offered are:

- **Standard** (delivered as 1 week Mon- Fri) or
- **5X1** (delivered 1 day a week for 5 weeks) or **Pump DAFNE** (delivered as 1 week Mon- Fri)

In response to COVID-19, some centres offered remote DAFNE courses, which is a blend of online learning, workbook activities and remote group sessions facilitated by DAFNE educators. Remote courses involve online learning from home each week and weekly group video support calls with other participants and a trained, there are two options:

- **Fully remote:** Online self-directed learning weeks 1-4. Group sessions weeks 1-5 delivered virtually.
- **Remote DAFNE (blended w/ F2F support):** Online self-directed learning weeks 1-4. Group sessions weeks 1-5 delivered either face to face or a blend of F2F and virtual.

In all courses groups of 6–8 participants (4-6 participants for remote courses) are given guidance by two certified educators (one diabetes specialist nurse and one diabetes dietitian), allowing participants to learn by experience and practice the key skills of estimating carbohydrate and adjusting insulin dose.

A two-to-three-hour group follow-up session is offered to participants at 4–12 weeks after each course to consolidate the skills acquired during the course and to review targets and goals.

Course participants are considered DAFNE graduates if they completely attend day 1 and day 2 and one day of the remaining 3 days. If one session is missed, they must complete the missed session(s) via one-to-one instruction within 12 weeks of the first day of the course or attend the missed session(s) at another DAFNE course within 12 weeks of the first day. However, it was not possible to determine from the current dataset whether an individual recorded as attending only 4 days/weeks had completed a one-to-one session or a session at another centre.

Supplementary Table 1 DAFNE face-to-face and remote course formats categorised using the template for intervention description and replication (TIDieR) checklist and guide²⁹

Name	Standard DAFNE	5 X 1	Pump DAFNE	Fully remote	Fully remote pump DAFNE	Remote DAFNE (blended w/ F2F support)
Why	DAFNE aims to help adults with type 1 diabetes lead as normal a life as possible, whilst also maintaining blood glucose levels within healthy targets, to reduce the risk of long-term diabetes complications.					
What	<p>Materials: Participants are provided with a course handbook, carbohydrate counting booklet and blood glucose/insulin/carbohydrate diary. Training and course delivery for educators is supported by an Educator Manual. For the remote courses access to the course content is provided online via the DAFNE modules on the Open University platform.</p> <p>Procedures: Skills based training in day-to-day carbohydrate estimation and insulin adjustment and across a range of situations including illness, exercise, alcohol, and hypoglycaemia. The training incorporates active group participation, reflective and experiential learning, practise, problem solving, and goal setting, to build autonomy, competence, and confidence in making informed decisions, within the framework of the DAFNE principles.</p>					
Who provided	3 DAFNE educators: a diabetes specialist nurse and a diabetes specialist dietitian and a diabetes consultant diabetologist / specialist registrar			1-2 DAFNE educators: diabetes specialist nurse and/or a diabetes specialist dietitian		
	HCP training is delivered online.			HCP training is delivered online.		
How	Face-to-face	Face-to-face	Face-to-face	Remote DAFNE uses a flipped classroom approach with online learning and remote group sessions. Online self-directed learning weeks 1-4. Group sessions weeks 1-5 delivered virtually.	Remote DAFNE uses a flipped classroom approach with online learning and remote group sessions. Online self-directed learning weeks 1-4. Group sessions weeks 1-5 delivered virtually.	Remote DAFNE uses a flipped classroom approach with online learning and remote group sessions. Online self-directed learning weeks 1-4. Group sessions weeks 1-5 delivered either face to face or a blend of F2F and virtual

Where	Classroom based, hospital or external site	Classroom based, hospital or external site	Classroom based, hospital or external site	Locally available platforms such as WebEx or MS Teams	Locally available platforms such as WebEx or MS Teams	Locally available platforms such as WebEx or MS Teams
When and How Much	1 week Mon – Fri; approx. 40 hours A two-to-three-hour group follow-up session at 4–12 weeks after each course.	1 day a week for 5 weeks; approx. 40 hours A two-to-three-hour group follow-up session at 4–12 weeks after each course.	1 week Mon – Fri; approx. 40 hours A two-to-three-hour group follow-up session at 4–12 weeks after each course.	1 day a week for 5 weeks; approx. 40 hours A two-to-three-hour group follow-up session at 4–12 weeks after each course.	1 day a week for 5 weeks; approx. 40 hours A two-to-three-hour group follow-up session at 4–12 weeks after each course.	1 day a week for 5 weeks; approx. 40 hours A two-to-three-hour group follow-up session at 4–12 weeks after each course.